

Exploring the potential of deep-sea shrimp oil based lipid microparticles as sustainable and nutritious ingredients for functional foods: A review

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Key Points:

- Shrimp oil lipid microparticles, rich in omega-3s, astaxanthin, phospholipids, and choline, offer great potential for functional foods.
- A successful integration journey requires collaborative efforts from academia, industry, and regulatory bodies.
- Ensuring safety and regulatory compliance is key to unlocking the potential of these microparticles in sustainable functional foods.

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Abstract

Functional foods with added health benefits have gained interest. Rising consumer awareness of health and the environment drives demand for sustainable and nutritious ingredients. Lipid microparticles from deep-sea shrimp oil, rich in omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, phospholipids, and choline, offer a promising solution. This review evaluates their potential as functional food ingredients, promoting wellness and sustainability in the industry. This paper discusses using lipid microparticles from deep-sea shrimp oil in functional foods due to their long-term viability and high nutritional value. The context section covers the rising popularity of functional foods and the importance of healthy, eco-friendly ingredients. The environmental benefits of deep-sea shrimp oil, such as reducing pressure on conventional fisheries and encouraging sustainability, are explored. The potential health advantages, such as improved cardiovascular health, cognition, and inflammation, are also examined. Recent studies on bioactive chemicals in deep-sea shrimp oil and their potential benefits to human health are highlighted. Meeting the rising demand for health and environmentally-friendly products, successful incorporation requires addressing regulatory and safety concerns. Collaboration among academia, industry, and regulatory bodies is crucial for realizing their full potential in the food industry's transition towards sustainability and health consciousness.

Keywords: Lipid microparticle, Functional foods, Deep Sea Shrimp oil, Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), Astaxanthin

1. Introduction

Deep-water shrimps are abundant in tropical waters all over the world and play a crucial role in the seafood business (Azofeifa-Solano and Cortés, 2020). Unfortunately, a significant portion of shrimp, particularly the heads and shells, is discarded during processing. However, these by-products have enough bioactive compounds and lipids to be useful (Nirmal et al., 2020). One of the by-products of the shrimp shell is chitin, a significant biopolymer. Chitin, in

its deacetylated form known as chitosan, is a crucial component of the encapsulation process due to its role as a wall material (Pakizeh et al., 2021). Lipids, enzymes, proteins, carotenes, and minerals are also present (Niamnuy et al., 2008). The pharmaceutical and food industries can benefit from these bioactive macromolecules (Aneesh et al., 2020). It is common knowledge that polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) are crucial, and that marine oils are a rich source of PUFA. When compared to other fish oils, the PUFA and pigment content of deep-sea shrimps is remarkable

(Aneesh et al., 2020). Carotenoids and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) like beta-carotene and astaxanthin are abundant in deep sea shrimp lipids. It has been found that astaxanthin is the most common carotenoid in shrimps. Cancer, high blood pressure, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease are all effectively combated by its biological actions (Aneesh et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021).

Due to the high concentration of unsaturated fatty acids, the deep sea shrimp oil's bioactive properties are limited. The health benefits will be nullified if the consumer uses oxidised oil or other substances (Guzmán et al., 2021). The cardiovascular benefits of fish oil may be nullified if it becomes oxidised, according to recent studies (Zhang et al., 2021). The direct inclusion of fish oil into foods has been a big problem for the food business due to its oxidative instability (Jamshidi et al., 2020). On the other hand, a food's overall appeal to the senses could be diminished if fish oil were added directly to the recipe. As a result, several different methods of food preservation have been developed to maintain the integrity of these volatile molecules and boost the general acceptability of food to the senses (Zhang et al., 2023). Fish oil is microencapsulated to prevent oxidation and facilitate its usage in food manufacturing (Beindorff and Zuidam, 2010). Proteins and/or carbohydrates are used as a dry matrix to encase the oil droplets, turning the liquid into a powder (Jiang et al., 2022). The microencapsulation method can also be used to cover up any fishy aftertastes or smells. Fortifying quick foods and other foods sold in powder form is now possible thanks to microencapsulated fish oil powder (Bansal et al., 2023). Polyunsaturated chemicals' hydrophobicity and high susceptibility to oxidative breakdown have a profound effect on their pharmacokinetics. As a result, these chemicals may have a reduced ability to be absorbed by the body and transported to where they're needed (Light and Karboune, 2022). In this context, micro/nanoparticles can provide a variety of options for avoiding the breakdown of therapeutic compounds and maximising their uptake, absorption, and bioavailability, and they can be used as a functional food.

Omega-3 fatty acids from shrimp oil can be made more stable and effective in functional foods by employing encapsulation technology. To prevent oxidation of the omega-3 oils, they can be encapsulated in a colloidal system like a liposome, emulsion droplet, nanostructured lipid carrier, or

microgel (Vishnu et al., 2017). These colloidal systems are versatile since they can be employed in liquid form or converted to a powdered form via spray-drying. Encapsulation can boost the bioavailability and functional characteristics of omega-3 fatty acids, in addition to increasing their stability (Vishnu et al., 2017). Encapsulated omega-3s, for instance, can be made to release gradually in the stomach, facilitating better absorption and utilisation. Omega-3 fatty acid functional meals that are encapsulated might have an enhanced flavour, texture, and visual appeal.

In conclusion, omega-3 sources derived from shrimp oil present a possible path toward enhancing the nutritional content of functional meals. Encapsulation technologies provide a means of delivering the health advantages of omega-3s to customers in a form that is both practical and aesthetically pleasing, notwithstanding the difficulties inherent in using these oils in food products.

2. Deep sea shrimps

Shrimps of the deep water belonging to the decapoda order. Since deep-sea shrimps contain many beneficial nutrients including long-chain omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids and the antioxidant astaxanthin, they are highly prized in international food markets. Similarly, the nutrient compositions of deep-water species are much more robust than those of shallow-water and coastal pelagic species (Kuberan et al., 2018). Bono et al., 2012 found that the total carotenoid content of deep-sea shrimp seafood is a strong source of nutrients and natural antioxidants such as astaxanthin and numerous carotenoids with minimal adverse effects, which may give selected health assistance to consumers. Some species are more in demand than others in both domestic and international markets because of their unique metabolic and nutritional benefits (Kuberan et al., 2018).

EPA and DHA, two types of omega-3 fatty acids, are abundant in the oil of deep-sea shrimps such as Krill (Ahmad et al., 2019). Inflammation reduction, heart health improvement, brain function support, and improved joint health are just some of the many health benefits linked to these fatty acids. Demand for deep-sea shrimp oil, a natural source of omega-3s, has remained high as people become more health conscious (Shahidi and Ambigaipalan, 2018).

Oil derived from deep-sea shrimp provides a sustainable alternative to marine fish oil. Shrinking fish populations has generated worries about the potential damage that over-fishing could do to marine ecosystems. Krill and other deep-sea shrimps have a faster reproductive rate than some fish species, making them more abundant and sustainable (Kawaguchi and Nicol, 2020). Less pressure is placed on declining fish populations when using oil from deep-sea shrimps instead of fish oil.

3. Oil extraction and Purification

Oil from deep sea shrimps can be derived from a wide variety of sources, including whole fish, individual organs, and even fish by-products (Nirmal et al., 2020). Traditional oil extraction utilises solvent-based techniques, typically involving a mixture of chloroform and methanol as the organic solvent. Fish tissue is ground and then added to a solvent combination (a 2:1 ratio of chloroform to methanol) to be extracted. The polar and non-polar lipid fractions can be separated with the help of water. Polar and nonpolar lipids can be found in the bottom chloroform layer, while other substances are found in the upper methanolic and water layers. The lipids are left after the chloroform layer is collected and the solvent is evaporated. This strategy has been used to successfully remove omega-3 PUFAs from fish muscle and liver (Vishnu et al., 2017). Physical methods, such as hydraulic pressing or heat extraction, can be used to separate the oil from fatty fish like salmon and tuna (Indelicato et al., 2023). When this occurs, organic solvent extraction can be used to get to the remaining oil. It's important to note that organic solvents used in fish oil extraction can leave behind harmful residues that could contaminate the surrounding area (Venugopalan et al., 2021). This has led to the development of greener alternatives including supercritical fluid extraction and enzyme-assisted extraction.

3.1. Green extraction methods

Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE), enzyme-assisted extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, and ultrasound-assisted extraction are only some of the green chemical methods that have been developed to extract fish oils and address these issues (Melgosa et al., 2021). The most popular environmentally friendly technique for obtaining omega-3 marine oils is supercritical fluid extraction (SFE).

Supercritical carbon dioxide (CO_2) is used as the solvent in this method, which is a greener and safer alternative to traditional organic solvents. SFE is a low-heat, high-yield technique for extracting oils with no harmful by-products or organic solvents. Furthermore, SFE manufacturing can be quickly scaled up to commercial levels (Krukonis, 2020). Another environmentally friendly technique is enzyme-assisted extraction, which uses enzymes to hydrolyse the fish tissues and extract the oils (Aitta et al., 2023). This technique has the potential to yield oils of superior purity and grade, and it is more selective and efficient than traditional solvent extraction procedures. The quantity of waste created during fish oil extraction can be minimised with the help of enzyme-assisted processes. There are environmental and health risks associated with the use of traditional solvents in the extraction of fish oils, and the development of green extraction methods is a promising field of research that can assist in addressing these issues.

4. Lipid chemistry (Chemical structure, and physicochemical properties)

Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, C20:5 n3) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, C22:6 n3), two marine LC-PUFA found in deep sea shrimp oil, have been shown to have numerous health benefits (Calder, 2021). Starting at the third carbon atom from the methyl-terminus, omega-3 fats are a type of long-chain polyunsaturated fat with methylene-separated double bonds (Wang et al., 2021). These are called "essential fatty acids" because humans need them but can't make them ourselves. Therefore, these fatty acids must be obtained from food consumption to meet needs. Like deep sea fish like cod, herring, mackerel, and shrimps, which live in cold, high-pressure habitats, shrimps have a high lipid (fat) content (Shillito et al., 2020). When compared to lipids found in other fish, those found in deep sea fish have a different chemical structure and content. Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), are the most abundant lipid components of deep sea fish (Figure 1). These PUFAs are extremely unsaturated and liquid at room temperature because of their lengthy carbon chains with numerous double bonds (Kapoor et al., 2021). In addition, deep water fish are able to go without food for extended periods of time because they store lipids in the liver and muscle tissues (Sikorski et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Structure of Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA).

Long-chain omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) like eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) are prevalent in cold-water fatty fish like salmon, tuna, and mackerel (Rincón-Cervera et al., 2020). When it comes to their biological activity and health advantages, EPA and DHA's distinct molecular structures are crucial. EPA has a 20-carbon structure with 5 double bonds; the first double bond is found on the molecule's third carbon from the omega end (the methyl end). EPA can be represented chemically as $C_{20}H_{30}O_2$. EPA has a crooked form because its double bonds are in the cis configuration, meaning they are on the same side of the carbon chain. This kink in EPA's structure makes it more pliable and fluid, facilitating its passage through cell membranes (Mason, Libby and Bhatt, 2020). In contrast, DHA's molecule contains 22 carbon atoms and 6 double bonds, the first of which is found on the third carbon from the omega end. DHA has the formula $C_{22}H_{32}O_2$. DHA shares EPA's bent structure because to its double bonds likewise being in the cis position. DHA, on the other hand, is more fluid and versatile since it is both longer and more highly unsaturated than EPA (Mason et al., 2020). Apart from this polyunsaturated fatty acid many saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids were present in the deep sea shrimp oil (Gulzar et al., 2020). The common fatty acids in deep sea shrimp oil and their physiological effect are well documented in Table 1.

The fatty acid pattern will vary with species, period, gender and location. The fatty acid patterns of shrimp oil are

varied, but it shows a higher concentration of palmitic acid, oleic acid, EPA, and DHA (Gulzar et al., 2020).

5. Sustainability Aspects

Utilizing deep-sea shrimp oil as a substitute for conventional fish oil provides a highly sustainable and environmentally conscious solution. Deep-sea shrimp oil is often extracted from shrimp heads and shells, which are by-products of shrimp processing and are otherwise discarded. This practice reduces the environmental strain associated with overfished species, as it relies on waste material rather than directly harvested fish. By mitigating the demand for conventional fish oils, this alternative decreases the need for extensive fishing, thereby protecting marine ecosystems from destructive practices such as overfishing and trawling, which are known to harm marine habitats and biodiversity (Gebremedhin et al., 2021). This sustainable approach also minimizes bycatch the unintentional capture of non-target species which is a significant challenge in traditional fishing methods. Supporting marine biodiversity, it aligns with global conservation efforts to maintain ecological balance. Moreover, by reducing waste through the utilization of shrimp by-products, this approach contributes to a circular economy, where resources are maximally used and waste is minimized. Deep-sea shrimp oil is rich in omega-3 fatty acids and other bioactive compounds, offering immense potential for the development of health and wellness products. These bioactives not only contribute to human health but also reduce reliance on endangered fish species traditionally used for oil extraction. Embracing this eco-friendly option is a step forward in addressing both human nutritional needs and the urgent requirement to conserve marine life. This dual benefit underscores its importance as a sustainable and responsible choice for the future (Gebremedhin et al., 2021).

6. Ecological Impact of Sourcing Deep Sea Shrimp Oil

Overfishing of omega-3-rich fish oil for popular fish species is yet another major ecological concern that leads to more widespread environmental issues. Excessive fishing disrupts marine food chains and contributes to the depletion of key fish populations, which affects ocean ecosystems' balance (Shantz et al., 2020). Moreover, with high

Table 1: Major fatty acids of deep sea shrimp oil and their physiological functions.

No	Name of fatty acid	Systematic Name	Carbon number	Physiological role	Reference
Saturated fatty acids					
1.	Lauric acid	Dodecanoic acid	C12:0	Against viral infections including influenza, the common cold; fever blisters, cold sores, and genital herpes caused by herpes simplex virus	Bartolotta et al., 2001
2.	Myristic acid	Tetradecanoic acid	C14:0	Role in post-translational protein changes	Legrand and Rioux, 2015
3.	Pentadecylic acid	Pentadecanoic acid	C15:0	Associated with a lower risk of developing type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease	Imamura et al., 2018
4.	Palmitic acid	Hexadecanoic acid	C16:0	Important regulators of inflammatory processes and secretion of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 and IL-6	Martín and Ramos, 2021
5.	Stearic acid	Octadecanoic acid	C18:0	Role in hormone production, cardiovascular health, gene transcription	Kris-Etherton et al., 2005
6.	Heneicosylic acid	Heneicosanoic acid	C21:0	Influence cell and tissue metabolism, function, and responsiveness to hormonal and other signals	Czumaj and Śledziński, 2020
7.	Behenic acid	Docosanoic acid	C22:0	Hair smoothening and conditioning property	Cater and Denke, 2001
8.	Lignoceric acid	Tetracosanoic acid	C24:0	Role in myelin lipids	Blanco et al., 2022

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No	Name of fatty acid	Systematic Name	Carbon number	Physiological role	Reference
Unsaturated fatty acids					
9.	Palmitoleic Acid	hexadec-9-enoic acid	C16:1n7	Beneficial effects on insulin sensitivity, cholesterol metabolism, and hemostasis. Also will prevent beta-cell apoptosis induced by glucose or saturated fatty acids	Morgan and Dhayal, 2010
10.	Heptadecenoic acid	cis-tetradec-10-enoic acid	C17:1n7	Cardioprotective role	Jenkins et al., 2015
11.	Elaidic acid	trans-9-octadecenoic acid	C18:1n9 t	Cardioprotective role	Tallima and El Ridi, 2018
12.	Oleic Acid	(9Z)-Octadec-9-enoic acid	C18:1n9 c	Protect Human Endothelial Cells from Oxidative Stress	Palomino et al., 2022
13.	Vaccenic acid	(11E)-11-octadecenoic acid	C18:1n7 c	Anti-diabetic effect	Jahreis and Dawczynski, 2020
14.	Eicosenoic acid	(11Z)-icos-11-enoic acid	C20:1n9	Promotes and regulates type 2 immune responses against intestinal and blood flukes	Tallima and El Ridi, 2018
15.	Erucic acid	cis-13-docosenoic acid	C22:1n9	Cardiac health	Kruger, 2014
16.	Nervonic acid	(15Z)-tetracos-15-enoic acid	C24:1n9	Nerve cells improvement	Li et al., 2019
Polyunsaturated fatty acids					
17.	Linolelaidic acid	(9E,12E)-Octadeca-9,12-dienoic acid	C18:2n6 t	Maintaining membrane fluidity of the transdermal water barrier of the epidermis	Whelan and Fritsche, 2013

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No	Name of fatty acid	Systematic Name	Carbon number	Physiological role	Reference
18.	Linoleic acid	(9Z,12Z)-Octadeca-9,12-dienoic acid	C18:2n6 c	Membrane fluidity	Whelan and Fritsche, 2013
19.	γ -Linolenic acid	(6Z,9Z,12Z)-Octadeca-6,9,12-trienoic acid	C18:3n6	Role in anti-inflammation and anti-proliferation	Antimanon et al., 2020
20.	α -Linolenic acid	(9Z,12Z,15Z)-octadeca-9,12,15-trienoic acid	C18:3n3	Precursor to the longer-chain n-3 PUFA, EPA and DHA, and particularly for supplying DHA for neural tissue	Sinclair et al., 2002
21.	Arachidonic acid	dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid	C20:3n3	Modulates the function of ion channels.	Tallima and El Ridi, 2018
22.	Eicosapentaenoic acid	cis-5,8,11,14,17-icosapentaenoic acid	C20:5n3	Antiatherosclerotic effects	Kris-Etherton et al., 2002
23.	Docosahexaenoic acid	cis-docosa-4,7,10,13,16,19-hexa-enoic acid	C22:6n3	Brain health, Cardioprotective role	Kris-Etherton et al., 2002; Vishnu et al., 2017

bycatch rates, the non-target species are often inadvertently caught, incurring major damage to marine biodiversity. This issue is further aggravated by habitat destruction resulting from fishing practices like trawling, which damages seabeds and interferes with the more sensitive habitats needed to maintain ecosystem health (Belshiasheela and Ghosh, 2020).

Deep-sea shrimp oil is another sustainable source. Since it is derived from shrimp by-products such as heads and shells, which go to waste, the oil provides a potential method of waste utilization that helps decrease strain on overfished fish varieties (Mathew et al., 2020). The reproduction rates of shrimp are greater than many fish species, therefore producing a more natural source of omega-3 fatty acids for a steady supply instead of the large-scale, ecologically destructive methods of harvesting needed for fish.

Shifting to shrimp oil not only serves the increasing demand for omega-3-rich products but also protects the marine environment by trapping bycatch and enhancing biodiversity. This greener approach is a step toward ocean ecosystems preservation, the sustainability of marine resources, and safe health provision for future generations (Mathew et al., 2020).

7. Health benefits

Prevention of cardiovascular disease, rheumatoid arthritis, high blood pressure, Crohn's disease, and Type 2 diabetes are only some of the many health benefits associated with fish oil intake. Fish oils, especially those high in omega-3 PUFAs as EPA and DHA, are associated with these advantages (Fatel et al., 2021; Vishnu et al., 2018). Many factors, including fish species, habitat, season, food, sex-

ual maturity, and sex, can affect the fatty acid profile of fish oils (Ahmed et al., 2022). Salmon and mackerel, for instance, have more omega-3 PUFAs than cod and tilapia, which are considered to be “leaner” fish. More harmful chemicals, like mercury and PCBs, may be found in fish caught in dirty waters. As a result, consumers who choose to supplement with fish oils should be mindful of where their oils are coming from. Fish oils strong in EPA and DHA and obtained from trustworthy, long-term fisheries are the ones to go for. The safety and purity of fish oil supplements should also be evaluated by regulatory agencies (Jairoun et al., 2020). Adding deep sea shrimp oil to functional foods may have positive effects on health due to the oil’s high omega-3 fatty acid concentration. Omega-3 fatty acids found in deep sea shrimp oil have been shown to have beneficial effects on cardiovascular health, brain function, and inflammation (Patel et al., 2022).

Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) are two omega-3 fatty acids that have been investigated extensively for their positive effects on cardiovascular health. There is evidence that EPA and DHA can help reduce the risk of cardiovascular disorders like heart attacks and strokes by lowering blood triglyceride levels, lowering blood pressure, and improving overall blood lipid profiles (Vishnu et al., 2018). Because of their anti-inflammatory properties, omega-3s can help keep blood vessels flexible and minimise the likelihood of atherosclerosis (the constriction and hardening of arteries). Omega-3 fatty acids have been linked in certain studies to a reduced risk of arrhythmias and improved cardiac rhythm. DHA, an omega-3 fatty acid, is particularly important for brain development and function during infancy and early childhood (Derbyshire, 2018). The risk of cognitive decline and neurodegenerative disorders is decreased and cognitive performance is enhanced in older persons who consume more omega-3 fatty acids, according to studies. The integrity of brain cell membranes is crucial for proper brain function, and recent studies suggest that omega-3s may have neuroprotective effects and help maintain this (Derbyshire, 2018). Heart disease, arthritis, and metabolic disorders are just a few of the many illnesses linked to chronic inflammation. Evidence suggests that omega-3 fatty acids, and especially EPA, can reduce inflammation (Singh, 2020). They assist regulate inflammation by blocking the synthesis of cytokines and prostaglandins, two chemicals that contribute to the inflammatory response. A healthy ratio of

omega-6 to omega-3 fatty acids, as is achieved by incorporating deep sea shrimp oil into functional meals, is thought to be helpful for lowering chronic inflammation (Singh, 2020).

8. Emerging Research on Bioactive Compounds in Deep Sea Shrimp Oil:

In addition to omega-3 fatty acids, the bioactive chemicals found in deep sea shrimp oil may be responsible for some of its purported health benefits (Figure 2).

8.1. Astaxanthin:

The red colour of deep sea shrimp oil comes from astaxanthin, a potent antioxidant, and carotenoid pigment. Protecting cells from oxidative damage, lowering inflammation, and bolstering cardiovascular health are all areas where astaxanthin has shown promise (Cao et al., 2023). New studies suggest astaxanthin may have neuroprotective qualities and enhance cognitive performance (Zhang et al., 2020). When compared to other well-known antioxidants like vitamins C, E, and beta-carotene, astaxanthin stands out for its extraordinary strength. Astaxanthin has been studied for its potential to protect against chronic diseases and age-related ailments by neutralising damaging free radicals in the body and lowering oxidative stress (Pereira et al., 2021). Because of its antioxidant capabilities, it is increasingly being used as a component in cosmetics intended to protect the skin from environmental aggressors and enhance its aesthetic appeal (Lima et al., 2021).

Evidence suggests that astaxanthin may also assist the eyes, warding off age-related macular degeneration and cataracts in the process (Yang and Wang, 2022). Astaxanthin is an attractive supplement for athletes and fitness lovers because of its potential to increase endurance, lessen exercise-induced exhaustion, and speed up muscle recovery (Drobnic et al., 2021). By reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, two major risk factors for cardiovascular illnesses, the chemical may also benefit cardiovascular health. Recent studies have shown promising results for the use of astaxanthin in reducing blood pressure and enhancing blood lipid profiles (Xia et al., 2020).

New research suggests astaxanthin has neuroprotective capabilities, able to transport across the blood-brain barrier,

Figure 2: Major Constituents of deep sea shrimp oil other than omega-3 fatty acids.

and shields brain cells. It has shown promise in animal studies for either halting or reducing the severity of neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's.

8.2. Phospholipids:

Deep sea shrimp oil, rich in phospholipids (Raju et al., 2021), holds significance for cell membrane function (Nicolson and Ferreira de Mattos, 2021). These phospholipids enhance the bioavailability of omega-3 fatty acids, potentially facilitating their absorption and utilization within the body (Markovic et al., 2020). Particularly crucial for omega-3s like EPA and DHA, phospholipids modify their interaction in the oil, as compared to triglyceride-based fish oil supplements (Raju et al., 2021). Phospholipid complexes, present in deep sea shrimp oil, enhance omega-3 bioavailability by structurally optimizing cell membrane integration. This heightened membrane fluidity can influence cellular signalling, nutrient transport, and other vital functions (Wong et al., 2022). Phospholipids also facilitate targeted omega-3 transport to cells, tissues, and organs, potentially benefiting brain health and cognitive function (Hachem and Nacir, 2022). Acting as antioxidants, phospholipids protect against oxidative damage, bolstering cellular health (Hachem and Nacir, 2022). While deep sea shrimp oil's phospholipids enhance omega-3 absorption, it's essential to consult a healthcare professional

before incorporating such supplements into your routine, as with any dietary modification.

8.3. Choline:

Choline, found in deep sea shrimp oil, is an essential vitamin for brain health and proper brain function (Shi et al., 2021). Choline is a building block for the neurotransmitter acetylcholine, which has been linked to improved memory and learning. The inclusion of these bioactive components in deep sea shrimp oil increases the potential health benefits of include this oil in functional meals; nevertheless, additional research is needed to fully understand the precise health consequences of these bioactive compounds. During crucial times of brain development, such pregnancy and infancy, the choline in deep sea shrimp oil may be beneficial (Li et al., 2023). Intake of enough choline aids in healthy brain development during pregnancy and may lower the chance of neural tube abnormalities (Obeid et al., 2022). Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter essential for learning, memory, and attention, while choline is a precursor to this neurotransmitter (Gallo and Gámiz, 2023). It promotes myelin production, which is necessary for rapid and accurate nerve signal transmission, and has neuroprotective qualities that help keep brain cell membranes from leaking (Gallo and Gámiz, 2023). Consumption of choline has been linked to enhanced memory and cog-

nitive function, and this association may be strengthened with increased consumption. In addition to its role in lipid metabolism, choline also protects the liver from fat accumulation. Through controlling homocysteine levels, it also benefits cardiovascular health (Gallo and Gámiz, 2023). Incorporating deep sea shrimp oil into functional foods is advantageous because of the oil's high concentrations of omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, phospholipids, and choline, all of which contribute to general health and wellness. As more is learned about these substances, deep sea shrimp oil will become an even more useful tool in the fight against disease and in favour of a healthy way of life.

9. Oxidation

Fish oil has several health benefits due to the high concentration of healthy omega-3 fatty acids it contains, but it has some drawbacks when used in cooking and baking. The development of hazardous hydroperoxides and other by-products is a major problem since they cause off-flavors and drastically reduce the shelf life of fortified foods (Nawar, 1996). Because of the risks associated with oxidation, adding fish oil directly to foods is not a good idea if you want to improve their nutritional value. The food industry's processing and storage procedures, which often involve high temperatures and exposure to air, can hasten the breakdown of these delicate fatty acids, further diminishing the items' appeal to the senses. To combat these issues, microencapsulation has emerged as a useful method for preserving the integrity of fish oil in food items by keeping it free from oxidation (Vishnu et al., 2017). Powdered fish oil is produced using a process called microencapsulation, in which the oil is broken down into tiny droplets and then encased in a dry matrix of coating materials (Venugopalan et al., 2021; Vishnu et al., 2017). This method not only protects the omega-3 fatty acids from oxidation, but it also aids in masking any unpleasant fishy aromas or flavours in the finished product (Venugopalan et al., 2021).

So, oxidation and sensory problems provide obstacles to the direct addition of fish oil to food products, but microencapsulation provides a new way to preserve the oil, increase its stability, and boost customer acceptance. Making fish oil more accessible and enticing to consumers who want to increase their consumption of omega-3 fatty acids for better health, producers can now easily add its health advantages

into a wide range of products using this technology (Vishnu et al., 2017).

10. Strategies to improve function

Lipids in fish oil are easily oxidised, which might result in the production of potentially hazardous chemicals like peroxides and hydroperoxides (Miyazawa, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to take action to increase the lipids in fish oil's oxidative stability. Many strategies have made for improving the function and oxidative stability of deep sea shrimp oil (Figure 3)

10.1. Antioxidant addition

Tocopherols, ascorbic acid, and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) are examples of natural and synthetic antioxidants that can be added to fish oil to slow the oxidation process and increase the lipids' oxidative stability.

10.1.1. Antioxidants commonly used to enhance the oxidative stability of fish oil:

Tocopherols (Vitamin E): Tocopherols are a class of antioxidant chemicals found in nature. Alpha-tocopherol, one of several forms of vitamin E, is the most popular in fish oil supplements due to its high biological activity. Tocopherols are effective because they eliminate free radicals, the extremely reactive chemicals responsible for oxidation. Tocopherols prevent the oxidation of fish oil by neutralising free radicals, preserving its nutritious content and extending its shelf life (El-Sayed and Izquierdo, 2022).

Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C): Vitamin C, or ascorbic acid, is an antioxidant that may be dissolved in water. Vitamin E, after having neutralised a free radical, is regenerated in large part by this nutrient. There is a synergistic effect between ascorbic acid and tocopherols that can increase the antioxidant protection of fish oil. Ascorbic acid also contributes to better oxidative stability by reducing iron ions, which can catalyse lipid oxidation in the presence of oxygen (Saleh et al., 2022).

Butylated Hydroxytoluene (BHT): The food and supplement industries frequently employ the utilisation of the synthetic antioxidant butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT). Inhibiting the production of free radicals and postponing

Figure 3: Deep sea shrimp oil oxidation prevention methods.

the commencement of lipid oxidation are two of its many beneficial effects. Although BHT has seen extensive application as an antioxidant, some have questioned whether or not its use in excessive doses has any safety or health risks. Because of these worries, some producers have looked into all-natural options (Hrebień-Filisińska, 2021).

Mixed Tocopherols: Some fish oil formulations use a combination of tocopherols, such as alpha, beta, gamma, and delta tocopherols, rather than only alpha-tocopherol. This combination may be more effective in the long run in stabilising fish oil and providing broader antioxidant protection (El-Sayed and Izquierdo, 2022).

Rosemary Extract: Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) is an herb that can be used to make an antioxidant-rich extract called rosemary extract. Carnosic acid and rosmarinic acid are among the active chemicals it contains; these acids have been demonstrated to have powerful antioxidant effects. Rosemary extract is replacing synthetic antioxidants in fish oil supplements because of its powerful antioxidant properties. It's important to think about things like dosage, stability, component interactions, and product shelf life when adding antioxidants to fish oil products. Fish oil produc-

ers also have an obligation to follow regulations and make sure that the antioxidants they use won't compromise the product's flavour or nutritional value (Hrebień-Filisińska, 2021).

10.2. Removal of pro-oxidants:

The oxidative character of fish oil lipids can be improved by removing pro-oxidants like transition metals and free fatty acids. Fatty acid modification: Refining, bleaching, and deodorising fish oil can alter its fatty acid composition, removing the more perishable polyunsaturated fatty acids and improving its overall oxidative stability (Venugopalan et al., 2021).

10.3. Protection against light and heat:

Fish oil should be stored in dark, cool places, and under inert gas, such as nitrogen, to prevent exposure to light and heat, which can accelerate oxidation and lead to the degradation of the oil's nutritional value and overall quality. Oxidation of fish oil occurs when it reacts with oxygen in the air, causing the development of harmful free radicals and rancidity, which can result in an unpleasant taste and smell (Jia et al., 2023).

10.4. Encapsulation:

Encapsulating fish oil in a protective matrix like gelatin, starch, or alginate improves the oil's oxidative stability and overall quality in many ways (Vishnu et al., 2017). The nutritious qualities of fish oil are protected and its shelf life is extended through encapsulation. The omega-3 fatty acids in fish oil are more readily absorbed by the body. The delicate lipids are protected by the matrix from the digestive enzymes, allowing for better intestinal absorption. In addition, encapsulation permits a measured, sustained release of fish oil in the gastrointestinal tract (Vishnu et al., 2017). This slow release lowers the chances of oxidation occurring during digestion and absorption. Furthermore, the encapsulation hides the fish oil's harsh taste and odour, making it more appealing and promoting consistent usage. Fish oil is protected from environmental elements including light, moisture, and temperature swings thanks to the encapsulation process. To keep the oil's nutritional value and freshness, its exposure to these factors should be kept to a minimum. Encapsulated fish oil is stable under a wide range of conditions, making it ideal for use in a wide range of food and supplement products. Such versatility allows for the development of omega-3 fatty acid-delivering functional meals, nutritional supplements, and pharmaceutical formulations that are stable against spoiling without sacrificing any of the health benefits (Venugopalan et al., 2021).

11. Encapsulation with biopolymers

To prevent oxidation, increase the oil's stability, and boost its absorption, fish oil is often encapsulated in a biopolymer. Biopolymers are non-toxic, naturally occurring polymers that can be regenerated indefinitely. Proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids are only some of the biopolymers that have been employed to encapsulate fish oil (Venugopalan et al., 2021). Fish oil has been encapsulated with whey protein, casein, and gelatin because these proteins can create durable coatings around the oil droplets. Heat or acid treatment denatures the proteins, allowing them to condense into a thin film that surrounds the oil droplets and prevents them from oxidising (Vishnu et al., 2017). The powder made by drying the resulting protein-coated droplets has many potential uses in the food and supplement industries. Starch, cellulose, and chitosan are only a few of the carbohydrates that have been utilised to encapsulate fish oil. Oil droplets can be stabilised and prevented from oxidising when these carbohydrates create gels or

films surrounding them. Because of its antibacterial and antioxidant characteristics, chitosan is frequently used for this purpose. Fish oil can also be encapsulated in lipids like phospholipids. Phospholipids can surround oil droplets in a stable bilayer, preventing them from oxidising and increasing their bioavailability. Encapsulation with phospholipids has been demonstrated to increase the body's uptake of fish oil's beneficial omega-3 fatty acids. Using biopolymers for encapsulating fish oil is an exciting new approach to increasing the oil's stability and bioavailability. The biopolymer used to encapsulate fish oil will be selected based on the final product's intended use and desired qualities (Yang et al., 2023).

Shrimp oil can be encapsulated using a number of different methods, each with its own set of benefits and potential uses. Here are some of the most typical approaches to shrimp oil encapsulation (Figure 4)

11.1. Spray Drying

The process of spray drying, which involves the transformation of a liquid or semi-liquid feed into a dry powder, is a common method of encapsulation. Shrimp oil encapsulation involves emulsifying the oil in a carrier solution to create tiny droplets. Atomizing the emulsion and exposing it to hot air causes the droplets to rapidly dry and solidify, creating enclosed particles. Spray drying can preserve bioactive chemicals from oxygen and light while maintaining excellent encapsulation efficiency and scalability (Geranpour et al., 2020).

11.2. Fluidized Bed Coating

Particles of shrimp oil can be coated using fluidized bed coating because they can be suspended in the coating medium. The particles of shrimp oil bind to the coating substance, which is often a biopolymer or lipid-based material. By encapsulating the oil, a stronger and more substantial barrier is created, making the oil more stable and resistant to oxidation. The controlled release properties of microcapsules can be manufactured via fluidized bed coating (Suhag et al., 2020).

11.3. Coacervation

The coacervate phase is formed when a second liquid phase encapsulates the shrimp oil droplets during the coacerva-

Figure 4: Most typical approaches to shrimp oil encapsulation

tion process. Coacervation can be accomplished in a number of ways, including by the use of oppositely charged polymers in a complex coacervation, or through the use of non-charged polymers in conjunction with changes in temperature or pH in a simple coacervation. The coacervate phase surrounds the shrimp oil like a shell, giving it increased stability and timed release (Bassijeh et al., 2020).

11.4. Emulsion templating

Emulsion templating entails combining shrimp oil with a hardening agent or precursor and distributing the resulting mixture in an oil-in-water emulsion. As the emulsion cools, the droplets become more stable, and the particles inside the emulsion become encased in a solid shell. Properties of the encapsulated particles, like mechanical strength and releasing characteristics, can be affected by the solidifying agent used (Chen et al., 2022).

11.5. Extrusion-Based Techniques

Uniform microspheres or particles can be produced by extruding a mixture of shrimp oil and encapsulating materials

via a small orifice. Co-extrusion and membrane extrusion are two types of extrusion-based techniques. These methods provide fine-tuned management over particle size and makeup, enabling the development of specialised formulations with desired properties (Jamshidi et al., 2020).

11.6. Nanoprecipitation

Shrimp oil and a water-miscible solvent (such ethanol or acetone) are rapidly mixed with a non-solvent (often water) in a process called nanoprecipitation. This process creates shrimp oil droplets on the nanoscale, each encased in its own protective shell. Shrimp oil nanoparticles, whose size may be adjusted by changing processing settings, are stable and may have better bioavailability as a result of encapsulation (Lammari et al., 2020).

11.7. Supercritical Fluid Technology

Supercritical carbon dioxide (SC – CO₂) is used as a solvent in supercritical fluid technology to break down shrimp oil and a coating. The SC – CO₂ evaporates during depressurization, leaving behind the solidified, encased particles.

The usage of temperature-sensitive materials is possible with this technology, and it is also considered environmentally beneficial (Aneesh et al., 2020).

Depending on the desired qualities of the encapsulated shrimp oil, the intended application, and the budgetary constraints, each encapsulation method has its pros and disadvantages. If you want your shrimp oil to be as stable, bioavailable, and effective as possible in a wide range of functional food applications, you need to choose the right encapsulation process. Since the encapsulating materials may come into contact with the food item, their safety and compatibility are also crucial (Aneesh et al., 2020).

12. Applications

The powdered form of encapsulated fish oil has several uses and is thus widely applicable. To provide consumers with a simple and effective source of omega-3 fatty acids and other critical nutrients, it is commonly used in nutritional supplements, where it is combined into capsules, pills, and powders. The powder is also widely accepted in the field of functional foods because of the ease with which it can be included into a wide variety of food items, including baked goods, beverages, and snacks, giving customers all the health advantages of omega-3s without sacrificing flavour or texture (Venugopalan et al., 2021). Additionally, encapsulated fish oil powder is used in pet food and aquaculture feed due to its adaptability in multiple feed applications. Animals' growth and well-being are improved when the powder is mixed into their meal. Encapsulated fish oil powder, which has several uses, has made its way into the beauty sector because to its many advantages. Powder added to moisturisers and serums helps skin retain moisture and stay healthy because of the important fatty acids it contains. Encapsulated fish oil powder also has an important function in the pharmaceutical industry. It's utilised in pharmaceuticals like pills and capsules to provide beneficial nutrients like omega-3 fatty acids and other antioxidants (Ajeeshkumar et al., 2021). The nutritional and health benefits of omega-3 fatty acids can be easily integrated into various products across different industries with the help of encapsulated fish oil powder, making it a valuable asset for promoting wellness and bolstering health-conscious decisions.

13. Challenges and Opportunities

Lipid microparticles derived from deep sea shrimp oil hold promise in functional foods, yet face challenges. Higher production costs could hinder market competitiveness and consumer acceptance. Antioxidants are crucial for maintaining nutritional value and preventing off-flavors. Sourcing sustainable shrimp oil without harming marine habitats is essential. Encapsulation methods may enhance stability and bioavailability. Collaboration between academia, research institutions, and industry can expedite technological advancements. Despite obstacles, the market for shrimp oil-fortified products, with potential therapeutic benefits, is expanding. Further research is imperative for efficacy. Through education and partnerships, deep sea shrimp oil's health benefits and environmental contribution can drive its integration into functional foods.

14. Conclusion and outlook

Lipid microparticles sourced from deep-sea shrimp oil offer a potential lipid solution for functional meals due to their low toxicity and extended shelf life. Abundant in omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, and phospholipids, these microparticles hold health benefits. Omega-3s support cardiovascular health, cognition, and inflammation control. Astaxanthin acts as a potent antioxidant, countering oxidative stress-related ailments. Phospholipids enhance the bioavailability of these components. Utilizing deep-sea shrimp oil for lipid microparticle production aligns with eco-friendly practices, minimizing waste, and adhering to circular economy principles. The resulting lipid microparticles can enrich various functional foods like yoghurt, milk, and dressings, expanding nutritious options for consumers. This approach harmonizes health-conscious consumer choices with sustainable resource utilization, offering a mutually beneficial outcome.

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All authors contributed to this work. Vishnu Kalladathvalappil Venugopalan and Mohamed Abdulla Hatha conceptualized the idea, Vishnu Kalladathvalappil Venugopalan, Akmal Hashim Hashimji, Tino Thamby, Arathi Kollath, Vishnuja Soman jointly wrote the manuscript draft. Mohamed Abdulla Hatha edited and revised this article. The final version was approved by all authors.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors affirm that there are no identifiable competing financial interests or personal relationships that might have influenced the research presented in this paper.

Data Availability Statement

This review paper does not generate any original data. All data discussed in this manuscript are derived from studies and datasets cited in the references that are publicly available. Datasets or materials related to this manuscript can be accessed from the sources mentioned in the reference list.

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